

Advanced Continuous Tow Shearing utilising Tow Width Control

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AFP layup limitations

AFP induced triangular shaped gaps on 3-dimensional surface. [1]

Geometry induced defects:
Resin rich areas and fibre discontinuities

High stress concentration

Areas of failure initiation

22.1% strength reduction for 0% gap-covered test specimens
10.8% strength reduction for 100% gap-covered test specimens (overlaps)
8.6% strength reduction using staggering method of gaps

[2]

While the **Continuous Tow Shearing (CTS)** process has been successful in eliminating defects in 1D angle variation layups by employing in-plane shear deformation, 3D composite layups pose a significant challenge due to triangular gaps with fibre discontinuities and resin-rich areas, leading to high stress concentration and areas of failure initiation.

A novel concept of a **Tow Width Control (TWiC)** mechanism is proposed, offering an innovative solution by enabling on-the-fly width adjustment of the tow. This mechanism eliminates tow drops and resin pocket defects while maintaining a constant fibre volume fraction, ensuring production of defect-free 3D composite layups. The implementation of the TWiC device within the CTS process unlocks the potential for achieving **ultra-high structural efficiency** in composite production.

AFP

CTS

CTS/TWiC

— Tow edge
- - - Reference tow path
| Head orientation
↑ Local fibre coordinate system

2D Scans

3D Scans

AFP

CTS

CTS/TWiC

Robot with mounted CTS/TWiC head.

Advantages

- Potential for achieving very high global fibre angles
- Production of complex shaped 3-Dimensional structures without tow gaps and overlaps
- No fibre discontinuities and resin rich areas (hot spots for damage initiation)
- Constant fibre volume fraction

2D scan of high global fibre angle CTS+TWiC layup with constant width in ply-level shifting direction with target boundaries overlay.

High global fibre angle layups

Comparison of global shift width variation between CTS*[3] and CTS+TWiC produced tows.

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[1] <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xK4gMDduHgA>

[2] O. Falcó, J.A. Mayugo, C.S. Lopes, N. Gascons, J. Costa, Variable-stiffness composite panels: Defect tolerance under in-plane tensile loading, Composites Part A, 63, 2014, pp. 21-31 (doi: 10.1016/j.compositesa.2014.03.022)

[3] B. C. Kim, P. M. Weaver, and K. Potter, "Manufacturing characteristics of the continuous tow shearing method for manufacturing of variable angle tow composites," Compos. Part A Appl. Sci. Manuf., vol. 61, pp. 141-151, Jun. 2014